

Quantum Interference and Statistical Mechanics

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In a previous note (1), we argued that quantum bound states may follow from a postulate regarding relative conditional probability at a point x i.e. the wavefunction $W(x)$ namely: $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle dx)$. This yields $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle = -i d \ln W / dx$ ((1)). Furthermore, it seems that $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle = -d/dx d/dx W / W$ ((2)) which may be utilized in a conservation of energy equation: $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W / W + V(x) = E$ (for the nonrelativistic case or the Klein-Gordon equation for the relativistic). As a result, there seems to be hump-like density behaviour whether one has a free quantum particle interacting with a two slit potential or a particle bound in a potential $V(x)$. We argue that the form of a wavefunction follows from statistical considerations and is the relative conditional probability to have p (or a p distribution) at x . $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle has a modulus of 1 everywhere, but also includes cycling which leads to experimentally observed humps i.e. interference patterns. Describing the probability by a real constant does not yield such results. It is possible to write $W(x) = \sum p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ for a bound state with the $\exp(ipx)$ "interfering", but one may alternatively consider $W(x)$ which forms its own "hump" pattern (like $\exp(ipx)$) based on the rules ((1)) and ((2)). In such a case, one does not need to consider the interference of $\exp(ipx)$'s. It is also possible to find "or" situations which exist at the $W(x)$ level. For example, one may combine $aW(x) + bW_1(x)$. In such a case, if $W(x)$ and $W_1(x)$ contain humps which may be positive or negative and so there is again interference, but one may consider $W_{\text{total}}(x)$ as the overall wavefunction which has its own "hump" pattern. In such a global view, one need not consider the interference of $W(x)$ and $W_1(x)$, but rather a scenario in which the particle forms a statistical pattern in which ((1)) and ((2)) hold. It is nevertheless interesting that one may use $W(x)$ and $W_1(x)$ together with the idea of interference to construct $W_{\text{total}}(x)$, but that does not necessarily mean one requires a physical mechanism i.e. a physical wave that interferes.

Quantum Mechanics and Statistical Mechanics

In (1), we argued that $\exp(ipx)$ used to describe the "wavefunction" (relative conditional probability to have p at x) of a free quantum particle follows from the statistical idea that a free particle should have the same probability to be at any x . This idea is coupled with an idea of "cycling" as a quantum particle seems to track its path in terms of a phase px , so $\exp(ipx)$ rather than a real constant is utilized. This leads to the observation that:

$$d/dx \exp(ipx) = ip \exp(ipx) \quad \text{and} \quad -d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx) = pp \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

We postulated in (1) that ((3)) represents general conditions which may be applied to more complicated scenarios such as a bound state. In particular:

$$W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i dx \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle) \quad ((5))$$

In that case:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \ln W = \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle \quad \text{and} \quad -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W = \langle p^2 \text{ at } x \rangle \quad ((6))$$

We argue that just as $\exp(ipx)$ leads to “humps” in a two-slit interference pattern, $W(x)$ may also have a similar hump pattern which may be seen in excited states of an oscillator or even a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls.

For a bound state with no net translation, we argue that $W(x)$ is real. This leads to an imaginary $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$.

W(x): Positive and Negative?

In the previous section we argued that $W(x)$ may be periodic, but this still begs the question of the sign of $W(x)$. It is possible to have a periodic function (e.g. $W(x) \cdot W(x)$) which is positive everywhere, so should $W(x)$ be positive as well for all x ?

Given that $W(x)$ is considered as a relative conditional probability (containing information in its x derivatives about average momentum and momentum squared), one may postulate that:

$$W_{\text{total}}(x) = W(x) + W_1(x) \text{ for some process} \quad ((6))$$

In other words, for usual probability theory an “or” situation leads to a summation of probabilities and this is extended to quantum wavefunctions. From ((1)) and ((2)), however, it seems that one develops “hump” (periodic) type behaviour in $W_{\text{total}}(x)$. $W(x)$ and $W_1(x)$ should also contain “humps” albeit different patterns. In order to create the required hump pattern for W_{total} , it seems $W(x)$ and $W_1(x)$ should add or cancel in different places. This suggests $W(x)$ should be positive and negative (although there can be exceptions like the ground state of the simple harmonic oscillator) to allow for “interference”. Interference involves the addition and subtraction of probability as well as addition and subtraction of component average values such as kinetic energy. For example, consider:

$$\langle p^2 \text{ ave at } x \rangle = \left[\text{Sum over } p \quad \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right] \cdot W(x) \quad ((7))$$

With $a(p) = a(-p)$ and $p/-p$, one has $2a(p) \cos(px)$ which is positive for some x and negative for others. Given a stochastic system, it should be possible to measure a particle in a p state i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. Such a state has $p^2/2m$. Interference occurs among various $p^2/2m P(p/x)$ terms in ((7)) to yield a final $\langle p^2 \text{ ave at } x \rangle$, but this average momentum squared also follows from ((1)) and ((2)) and an energy equation. One does not need to think in terms of ((7)) and component wavefunctions. Thus, one is not “forced” to consider interference, although it is useful in removing resolution which may be lost as one moves from a $\cos(px)$ (high p) to the overall hump

resolution of $W(x)$. It is not resolution (i.e. the $W(x)$ pattern) which is affected, but also average $pp/2m$ etc.

Scattering Example

In quantum mechanics a steady state scattering from a potential may be written in a time-independent manner with:

$$W(x) = A \exp(ipx) + f(\theta, \phi) \exp(ikr)/r \quad ((8))$$

Particles stream in with $\exp(ipx)$ and some are scattered. Nevertheless $W^*(x)W(x)$ includes interference between $\exp(ipx)$ and $f(\theta, \phi) \exp(ikr)/r$. Normally, one would argue that $\exp(ipx)$ loses particles because they scatter out, yet mathematically it is through an interference process that one sees this removal. One may ask: What is physically interfering to remove the particle? This is not a physical wave problem, but rather a probability wave problem. Nevertheless, the idea of a probability wave has physical implications in that it is responsible for the distinct hump patterns which so often appear in $W(x)$ and are still visible in the physically observable $W^*(x)W(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one treats the wavefunction $W(x)$ as a relative conditional probability and imposes ((1)) and ((2)), one does not really need to consider interference of component pieces e.g. $\exp(ipx)$ in ((7)), even though such interference is at the least a convenient mathematical tool. Ultimately, even in the case of $W_{total}(x) = W(x) + W_1(x)$, it is $W_{total}(x)$ which is of concern. This probability is linked to average momentum and momentum squared by $-i \frac{d}{dx} \ln W_{total} = \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ and $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_{total} / W_{total} = \langle p^2 \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ and has a corresponding hump pattern.

Reference

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Phase Shift of $\exp[i \langle p \text{ average at } x \rangle \Delta(x)]$ for Bound Quantum Systems (preprint, zenodo, 2020)